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THE ENTREPRENEDU PROGRAMME: AN EDUCATIONAL AND SCALABLE MODEL FOR ENHANCING THE EUROPEAN ENTREPRENEURIAL ECOSYSTEMS

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Abstract

European entrepreneurial ecosystems are encountering heightened global competition, however bridging the innovation gap within European countries and regions remains crucial to furnish educational schemes and supportive mechanisms for youth and startups. Technologically driven sectors such as spacetechnology, deeptech and climate tech offer fertile ground for innovation, but new entrepreneurs, students and researchers often lack the necessary expertise to build resilient and prosperous businesses. To provide the right know-how, and to support the birth of innovative ideas and ultimately strengthen entrepreneurial ecosystems the programme ENTREPRENEDU - Enhancing Entrepreneurial Ecosystems for Education - brings together several innovation stakeholders and educational entities from 6 different European countries, 3 low/moderate innovative regions Italy, Bulgaria and Greece and 3 high innovative regions Belgium, Germany and Ireland. ENTREPRENEDU - is a Horizon Europe financed programme, coordinated by E. Amaldi Foundation, that aims to create a more innovative, entrepreneurial and sustainable European higher education system. The programme is conceived for students, young entrepreneurs and start-ups working in the space economy, deep tech and green and digital transition and aims at creating a high replicable and scalable Venture Building Programme for both businesses and educational systems via a series of 3 Hackathons, developed at regional level, supporting developed concepts and ideas to become concrete solutions. ENTREPRENEDU aims to foster the birth of innovative ideas that will have an impact on both the Green Deal and the SDGs, as well as on gender equality, with the goal of having concrete projects for a better and more sustainable world. This second paper closely follows the results presented last year and aims to provide all relevant updates from last year's discussion and a complete overview of ENTREPRENEDU's scalable and replicable Venture Building Programme, presenting the Venture Building Syllabus and providing a comprehensive overview of the 3 organised hackathons and the Mentoring Programme. The study will then present the best practices implemented by the consortium to engage students and young entrepreneurs from the space sector and beyond to provide them with entrepreneurial skills tailored to their needs to become successful entrepreneurs.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, innovation ecosystems, venture building, hackathon, mentoring, business acceleration

1. Introduction

The European innovation landscape is at a pivotal moment, marked by increasing global competition. Despite significant progress, there is an urgent need to bridge the innovation gap that still exists between different European countries and regions. This calls for the development of educational programs and support systems that foster young people's aspirations and stimulate startup growth. However, several challenges

have emerged, including knowledge gaps, poor coordination, financial constraints, regional disparities, and the risks associated with scaling up.

In this dynamic context, innovators, educational institutions, and entrepreneurs play a crucial role as the main drivers of technological progress, economic growth, job creation, and overall societal well-being. To fully realise this potential, it is essential for educational institutions to forge strong collaborations with the

industry, equipping students with the entrepreneurial skills needed to navigate the rapidly evolving innovation landscape.

According to the 2021 European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS), innovation performance across the EU has shown an encouraging upward trend, with an average increase of 12.5% since 2014. However, the ongoing divide between high-performing and lower-performing countries highlights the need for more comprehensive efforts. Notably, five EU countries—Cyprus, Estonia, Greece, Italy, and Lithuania—have seen performance improvements exceeding 25 percentage points. Nevertheless, many European countries, including Italy, Cyprus, Malta, Slovenia, Spain, Czechia, Lithuania, Portugal, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Slovakia, Poland, Latvia, Bulgaria, and Romania, remain classified as moderate or emerging innovators.

In these moderate or emerging innovation countries, numerous challenges persist. Europe's business environment remains fragmented, a situation worsened by events like Brexit and the disruptive impact of the coronavirus pandemic. This fragmentation has limited local economic support for entrepreneurs, stunting growth potential. Additionally, this fragmented landscape has created information asymmetry among stakeholders, contributing to perceived risks for both investors and companies. As a result, there is reluctance to establish strong, technology-friendly ecosystems and districts, leading to business isolation.

A significant issue is the lack of coordination between EU and national-level innovation ecosystems, encompassing both business and education. This lack of alignment and synergy necessitates a significant improvement in the effectiveness of support through a more cohesive approach at the EU level. The failure to bridge the coordination gap between existing models, as well as between the educational and private sectors, has resulted in duplicated assessment costs, missed economies of scale, and lost opportunities for both youth and businesses.

While Knowledge Management has emerged as a strategic tool for enhancing organisational performance and competitive advantage over the past two decades, it remains notably absent from educational systems. This omission has serious consequences, leaving young people and aspiring entrepreneurs without access to vital entrepreneurship education, thereby increasing the risk of startup failure. Indeed, 2019 statistics show that the startup failure rate was around 90%, with 21.5% failing in the first year, 30% in the second, 50% in the fifth, and a staggering 70% by their tenth year.

The lack of expertise and collaboration between businesses and educational systems, in both less and more innovative regions, is a major barrier to unlocking the full potential of European entrepreneurship. Furthermore, the disparity between emerging, modest, and advanced innovation regions has led to a concentration of European businesses in a few developed innovation hotspots, primarily in Northern and Western Europe. For young entrepreneurs, navigating the complex landscape of acceleration and incubation options has been a significant challenge, despite the fact that companies using these services have an impressive survival rate of 87%, compared to just 44% for those without such support.

In response to this complex and evolving situation, the ENTREPRENEDU project (Enhancing Entrepreneurial Ecosystems for Education) has been launched to address these challenges. ENTREPRENEDU aims to provide crucial solutions that empower both businesses and educational systems, steering European entrepreneurship toward a more promising and sustainable future.

2. ENTREPRENEDU - Goal, objectives, planned outcomes and strategic positioning in the European context

The ENTREPRENEDU project aims to establish a highly replicable and scalable educational model for European entrepreneurial ecosystems. In this regard, the actions promoted by ENTREPRENEDU are primarily focused on enhancing network connectivity within and between innovation ecosystems to foster sustainable business growth with significant societal impact. ENTREPRENEDU thus aims to support youth and aspiring startup founders in acquiring the necessary skills to overcome the barriers to accessing finance and markets.

In doing so, the project aims to act as a bridge between the educational and business sectors while strengthening connections among various European regions at different levels of innovation. By carefully assessing their needs and aligning them with potential investors, ENTREPRENEDU wants to provide these individuals with the tools and knowledge required to establish themselves in the market.

These tools include stimulating technology transfer, expanding networking outreach, and facilitating matchmaking with investors, in addition to providing funding opportunities. The objective of the project is then to create a Venture Building Programme for sharing capacity and knowledge, contributing to strengthening the European entrepreneurial ecosystems.

To achieve this ambitious goal and provide selected companies with the conditions to enter the market within this framework, the project is structured in four main phases:

- **Needs Identification:** The initial phase centred on identifying the needs of both the education and business ecosystems that could benefit from the solutions developed by ENTREPRENEDU. This phase paid specific attention to three key targets: citizens, SMEs, and public administrations. Best practices and success stories of startups and other entities that have devised business knowledge solutions for education were identified. Local/regional accelerators and incubators were actively engaged, involving them in workshops and seminars to share best practices. Addressing the lack of entrepreneurship skills within the European education business skills model was the primary focus in this phase.
- **Cross-Fertilization and Challenge Generation:** The second phase involved translating the identified needs into specific challenges. These challenges served as the topics addressed and the concepts delivered during ENTREPRENEDU's three hackathons, whose aim was to involve individuals between the ages of 18 and 40 and newborn start-ups to involve 90 business ideas.
- **Support for Selected Startups:** The third phase focused on supporting 12 startups and teams selected during the ENTREPRENEDU hackathons. Over a six-month period, these startups were meant to receive up to 60 hours of mentoring (720 hours in total) through webinars and coaching workshops. The mentoring covered strategic topics such as tech due diligence, access to finance, business model design, education data and services, acceleration programs, and investment readiness.
- **Validation of the Venture Building Programme:** The ENTREPRENEDU Venture Building Program is planned to be validated within the educational partners of the ENTREPRENEDU consortium. The Venture Building Programme Syllabus is structured on the six strategic topics defined in the mentoring activities of the third phase. A minimum number of 90 students are planned to be selected via internal calls for applicants

to participate in the programme, which will be offered in the first semester of the academic year 2024-2025 as an extracurricular activity.

Ultimately, ENTREPRENEDU gives priority to concepts and ideas that can have an impact on both the Green Deal and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), as well as promoting gender equality. The ultimate goal is then to have all selected finalists with concrete projects that contribute to a better and more sustainable world.

3. Project outcomes to date

This section reports the outcomes of the first two years of the project. In particular, a literature review on methods to address regional disparities in European entrepreneurship ecosystems is reported, the outcomes and best practices of the ENTREPRENEDU hackathons organised in Italy, the outcomes of the Mentoring Programme and the final version of the Venture Building Programme planned for the last stage of the project are reported.

3.1 Literature Review

Hackathons have become a popular tool for enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems in Europe (Stam, 2015). These events bring together individuals with diverse backgrounds to collaborate on innovative solutions to address various challenges (Bouncken & Kraus, 2022). The structure and format of hackathons, characterised by time-bound collaboration and the emphasis on rapid prototyping, can serve as a valuable tool for enhancing the European entrepreneurial ecosystem (Martirena et al., 2019). Hackathons can provide a dynamic environment for ideation, networking, and the development of entrepreneurial skills, all of which are essential for an impactful entrepreneurial ecosystem (Angarita & Nolte, 2020).

Research has shown that hackathons play a crucial role in driving service innovation strategies and enhancing entrepreneurial intention (Kamariotou & Kitsios, 2022). By providing a platform for collaboration and creativity, hackathons contribute to the growth and development of the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Europe. Furthermore, the Evolution of digital Hackathons, Incubators, and Accelerators highlights the importance of allocating resources to support entrepreneurship ecosystems (Kollwitz & Dinter, 2019; Soltani et al., 2014).

Hackathons can also serve as a valuable tool for strengthening the overall entrepreneurial ecosystem in Europe. By bringing together a diverse array of stakeholders, including entrepreneurs, investors, industry experts, and policymakers, hackathons can

foster meaningful connections, facilitate knowledge sharing, and catalyze collaborative efforts. As highlighted by (Bertello et al., 2022) the effectiveness of each component within an entrepreneurial ecosystem is moderated by the interactions and relationships among the various actors.

Through hackathons, participants can expand their professional networks, gain exposure to new ideas and technologies, and establish potential partnerships and collaborations. These events can also serve as a platform for showcasing innovative solutions, attracting the attention of investors and potential customers, and creating opportunities for further development and commercialization.

Hackathons can also serve as a powerful tool for networking and building connections within the European entrepreneurial ecosystem. These events provide a platform for participants to interact with a diverse range of stakeholders, including entrepreneurs, investors, industry experts, and policymakers. (Vanaelst et al., 2018) (Fostering Innovation-driven Entrepreneurship in Europe, n.d)

The development of new professional relationships, exchange of ideas and knowledge, and opportunities for collaboration can arise from hackathons. As participants engage in intensive team-based collaboration and problem-solving, they have the chance to showcase their skills, build their professional networks, and potentially identify new partners or collaborators (Alvedalen & Boschma, 2017).

Overall, hackathons have emerged as valuable tools for enhancing the European entrepreneurial ecosystem. They facilitate collaboration, innovation, and the development of new ideas that can drive economic growth and regional prosperity. By bringing together entrepreneurs, researchers, and experts, hackathons play a vital role in overcoming weak network problems and fostering a culture of innovation in entrepreneurial ecosystems (Rijnsoever, 2020).

Based on the above, hackathons were identified as an effective means of accessing the entrepreneurial mentoring journey envisaged within ENTREPRENEDU.

3.2 Hackathons - overview, results, feedback

Three Hackathons with the brand name “HackTheBusiness” took place, one in Italy, one in Greece, and one in Bulgaria. During the events, participants had the opportunity to participate in synchronous frontal mentoring sessions led by a team of experts who shared expertise and best practices in various key aspects of structuring business ideas. These

sessions covered a variety of topics, including business model discovery, activating the potential within ideas, strategies for raising funds from Business Angels, building future-oriented business ideas, and the path from idea conception to concrete impact in the marketplace. The goal of this mentoring was to provide participants with the tools and understanding needed to develop their business ideas in depth. In addition to general mentoring sessions, great emphasis was placed on ad-hoc mentoring sessions with individual teams. These customised sessions allowed participants to get direct feedback and advice on specific issues related to their business ideas. This close interaction with experts fostered the growth and improvement of the business proposals presented by the teams. The following are brief descriptions and achievements of the 3 Hackathons:

- HackTheBusiness Italy took place in Rimini during the “We Make Future 2023” (15-17 June 2023), the largest digital innovation fair in Italy, counting 60 '000 attendees and 2 '000 startups, where a dedicated space was reserved for hacking, workshops, and pitches. The central theme of this business challenge was deeptech to solve 3 main challenges: *Innovating Society with Satellite Data and New Space Technologies*, *Sustainable Food Systems for Future Generations* and *Mitigating and Adapting to the Effects of a Changing World*. HackTheBusiness Italy, with the support of 5 community partners, counted a total of 43 applications with 30 business ideas from which 4 winners were selected.
- HackTheBusiness Greece was the first entrepreneurship and educational Ideation Contest that took place on a national level in Greece, aiming to spark business ideas in the field of space technologies. It was held under the aegis of the Ministry of Digital Governance and consisted of 2 different phases. In the First Phase (03-05 November 2023), 4 different local competitions (physical events) took place simultaneously in different cities in Greece in collaboration with local Universities: Athens (National Technical University of Athens), Thessaloniki (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki), Volos (University of Thessaly), Xanthi (Democritus University of Thrace). In the Second Phase (25 November 2023), the local winners of each local competition gathered in Athens to pitch their ideas against each other in front of a jury of 6 experts. HackTheBusiness Greece received a total of 108 applications with 35 business

ideas with members from 4 different universities in Greece. In the finals, 12 teams competed, and 4 winners were selected. With 14 supporters (sponsors and community partners), the event was a significant milestone for the Greek entrepreneurial ecosystem.

- HackTheBusiness Bulgaria took place on March 26th and 27th at the Innovation Forum “John Atanasoff” of Sofia Tech Park, bringing together young entrepreneurs, researchers, and early-stage startups to pitch innovative and sustainable business ideas. With the support of 4 community partners, the event attracted 61 applications, resulting in 29 business ideas. From a pool of 23 entries, 5 winners were selected.

Regarding the communication, branding material for all three events including the communication kit, press releases, posts, landing page, registration tool, flyers, badges etc. have been prepared. In addition, 5 warm-up sessions were organised by the ENTREPRENEDU partners as part of the pre-hackathon campaign in order to disseminate the events and attract participants. Also, dedicated web pages for each competition have been prepared, serving as central hubs for vital information such as competition details, agendas, and registration portals. This streamlined approach facilitated seamless navigation for participants, enhancing their overall experience and fostering greater interaction with the event.

3.3 Mentoring Programme - results and feedback

The winning teams of each Hackathon entered the ENTREPRENDU mentoring programme to improve their business idea. Hereby, the four to five winning teams of each Hackathon formed a cohort, resulting in three cohorts completing the programme. To structure the programme according to the needs of the participants, a demand analysis was conducted by Fraunhofer IPK with the winners of the Italian Hackathon. The derived topics from this analysis were matched with the experiences of the mentoring partners of the project, resulting in a six module curriculum:

- Mentoring Module 1: Business Model Development (Mentor: Fraunhofer IPK)
- Mentoring Module 2: Crafting a Unique and Competitive Value Proposition (Mentor: LUISS)
- Mentoring Module 3: Your Idea Pitch: from Tech Feasibility to Product Development (Mentor: FEA)
- Mentoring Module 4: Investment Pitch and Quantifying Your Funding Needs (Mentor: EBAN)
- Mentoring Module 5: Entrepreneurial Business Planning (Mentor: Corallia)
- Mentoring Module 6: Access to Finance and Related Funding (Mentor: Cleantech Bulgaria)

The mentoring programme was facilitated online and consisted out of three distinct phases. The initial phase focuses on delivering standardised content through webinars and training videos, providing participants with foundational knowledge and basic assessments like quizzes. In the second phase, personalised development takes priority with live mentoring, workshops, and Q&A sessions tailored to individual needs. The final phase emphasises reflection and feedback, where participants review their progress and goal achievements in a one-on-one session with their mentor. Each of the partners provided ten hours of mentoring, leading to a total mentoring amount of 60 hours per participant. In total, 12 participating teams made it to the final stages of the programme. The programme aimed to foster the business ideas of the participants and enable them to reach at least one of the following milestones:

- Define tailored business models and develop comprehensive business plans at the European level
- Apply for various regional initiatives and European financial support instruments
- Create an impactful pitch presentations and identifying investor events to engage with private stakeholders
- Identify and enrol in further acceleration programmes at regional, national, and European levels

The results of the mentoring programme show that:

- 12 teams defined their business model during the mentoring programme.
- 9 teams developed a business plan at the European level
- 10 teams applied to one or more Regional initiatives and/or European financial support instruments
- 12 teams defined a pitch presentation and identified investor events
- 7 teams identified and enrolled in further acceleration programmes at regional, national or European level

Therefore, the participating teams reached at least one milestone highlighting the programme's positive impact. Further, participants were also asked to provide feedback on their experience with the mentoring programme. The overall feedback from the mentoring

programme was highly positive, with participants from all cohorts expressing strong satisfaction with the structure, content, and delivery of the modules. Key strengths included the expert guidance from mentors, the practical focus of the modules, and the systematic approach to entrepreneurial education. The modules offered participants valuable insights and hands-on learning opportunities.

However, there were some areas for improvement. Participants suggested better integration between modules to reduce overlap, extending the programme's duration for more in-depth exploration of topics, and offering more flexible scheduling to accommodate participants' busy schedules. Additionally, a need for clearer guidance on applying lessons in sequence and more support in areas like Human Resources Management (HRM) and leadership were identified. Overall, while the programme was highly effective, these improvements could further enhance its impact.

3.4 The Venture Building Programme

In the effort to close the gap between high and low/moderate innovation regions within the European entrepreneurial ecosystem, the final step of the ENTREPRENEDU programme is the implementation of a comprehensive Venture Building Programme. This programme, with its goals and initiatives, has the potential to foster entrepreneurship, drive innovation, and strengthen collaborations between educational institutions and the private sector. The first step in establishing the Venture Building Programme was the creation of a business creation syllabus, incorporating comments and feedback from participants in the previous phases.

The final version of the syllabus followed feedback and to enhance its practical applicability, and involved insights from academic and industry stakeholders to ensure the content was comprehensive and relevant. A comprehensive database of all relevant materials was created to enable customization of the syllabus into three versions tailored to the needs of students in the 3 different countries of each academic partner co-involved in the validation. All material was reviewed and validated by an external expert to further improve the effectiveness of the syllabus and related material and to assess its relevance.

The final version of the Venture Building Syllabus includes 6 educational modules, which are given below:

- Module 0: Venture Building Group Project
- Module 1: Problem Identification and Validation, Idea Generation

- Module 2: Solution Development and Validation, Crafting Value Proposition
- Module 3: Market Discovery
- Module 4: Business Model Development
- Module 5: Access to Finance and Funding

As part of the validation phase of the Venture Building Programme, academic partners were tasked with launching calls for students to participate in the programme. At the time of this paper, one call has been launched in Italy, receiving 60 applications. On the other hand, the remaining calls in Greece and Bulgaria are currently in the organisation process, but similar numbers are expected. These calls will be crucial for gathering diverse student participation, which will further validate and enrich the Venture Building Programme through practical implementation and feedback.

4. Conclusions

In response to these complex challenges, the ENTREPRENEDU project has been crafted to provide innovative solutions that strengthen both business and education systems, driving European entrepreneurship towards a more sustainable and prosperous future. As discussed, the project's goals are ambitious yet crucial, focusing on enhancing network connectivity within and across innovation ecosystems, supporting young and aspiring start-up founders, and developing a venture-building programme to share entrepreneurial knowledge and skills.

The project addresses the specific needs of citizens, SMEs, and public administrations, while also promoting gender equality and aligning with both the Green Deal and the Sustainable Development Goals. Notable progress has already been made, including the organisation of three ENTREPRENEDU hackathons, titled HackTheBusiness, which brought together 111 teams of young students, entrepreneurs, and start-ups. These hackathons generated innovative business ideas and provided mentoring to help transform these ideas into viable ventures. Additionally, the implementation of a Mentoring Programme has involved 13 teams awarded during the hackathons.

As the project enters its final phase, it will focus on the final validation of the Venture Building programme, which will engage over 90 students from three educational institutions. This programme will be the cornerstone of ENTREPRENEDU's mission.

In our view, the ENTREPRENEDU project represents a critical step in closing the innovation gap in Europe. By fostering collaboration, delivering training, and creating opportunities for entrepreneurs, it aims to empower

individuals and regions to fully realise their innovation potential. As the project reaches its conclusion, it is poised to make a lasting contribution to the transformation of Europe's entrepreneurial ecosystem, making it more inclusive, sustainable, and globally competitive.

References

State of New Jersey Governor, 2022

<https://nj.gov/governor/news/news/562018/approved/20180725a.shtml>

Financial Times, 2020

<https://www.ft.com/content/7cf571bc-518b-11ea-a1ef-da1721a0541e>

EIB, 2020

<https://www.eib.org/en/publications/investment-report-2020>

Investopedia, 2022

<https://www.investopedia.com/articles/personal-finance/040915/how-many-startups-fail-and-why.asp#:~:text=In%202019%2C%20the%20failure%20rate,70%25%20in%20their%2010th%20year.>

Alvedalen, J., & Boschma, R. (2017). A critical review of entrepreneurial ecosystems research: Towards a future research agenda. *European Planning Studies*, 25(6), 887–903.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/09654313.2017.1299694>

Angarita, M. A. M., & Nolte, A. (2020). What Do We Know About Hackathon Outcomes and How to Support Them? - A Systematic Literature Review. *International Conference on Collaboration Technologies and Social Computing*.

<https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:221380861>

Bertello, A., Bogers, M. L. A. M., & De Bernardi, P. (2022). Open innovation in the face of the COVID-19 grand challenge: Insights from the Pan-European hackathon 'EUvsVirus'. *R&D Management*, 52(2), 178–192. <https://doi.org/10.1111/radm.12456>

Bouncken, R. B., & Kraus, S. (2022). Entrepreneurial ecosystems in an interconnected world: Emergence, governance and digitalization. *Review of Managerial Science*, 16(1), 1–14.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-021-00444-1>

Kamariotou, M., & Kitsios, F. (2022). Hackathons for Driving Service Innovation Strategies: The Evolution of a Digital Platform-Based Ecosystem. *Journal of Open*

Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity, 8(3), 111. <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc8030111>

Kollwitz, C., & Dinter, B. (2019). What the Hack? - Towards a Taxonomy of Hackathons. *International Conference on Business Process Management*. <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:201616413>

Martiarena, A., Möslinger, M., & Kert, K. (2019). *Connecting with the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem. KJ-NA-29988-EN-N (online)*. <https://doi.org/10.2760/272399> (online)

Rijnsoever, F. J. van. (2020). Meeting, mating, and intermediating: How incubators can overcome weak network problems in entrepreneurial ecosystems. *Research Policy*, 49(1), 103884. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2019.103884>

Soltani, P., Pessi, K., Brodén, K., & Wernerer, I. (2014, September). Hackathon – A method for Digital Innovative Success: A Comparative Descriptive Study. *Proceedings of the 8th European Conference on Information Management and Evaluation, ECIME 2014*.

Stam, E. (2015). Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Regional Policy: A Sympathetic Critique. *European Planning Studies*, 23(9), 1759–1769.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/09654313.2015.1061484>